

Alternative to Antibiotics: A Novel Approach to Non-antibiotic Therapy or a Part of Conventional Therapy?

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Abstract

In the era of increasing consumption and demand of antibiotics along with the development of antimicrobial resistance, there is a need to develop novel strategies and compounds having antimicrobial properties for non-antibiotic therapy or which can be used as a part of antibiotic therapy in order to fulfill the increasing demand of antibiotics and reduce the development of antibiotic resistance. The present article introduces some of the novel strategies and compounds such as Plants and plant extracts, Nano-Antimicrobial materials, Phage therapy, antimicrobial peptides, CRISPR-Cas, Immunity modulating agents and Inhibitors targeting pathogenicity which can be adopted and some of them are in clinical use, in order to combat diseases and improve the health and welfare of humans and livestock.

Introduction

The discovery of antibiotics was a boon for mankind. The clinical use of antibiotics was considered to be the greatest medical breakthrough in the 20th century. The use of antibiotics dates back to the use of mouldy bread to treat open wounds in China, Serbia, Egypt and Greece. However, the concept of chemotherapy is widely accredited to Paul Ehrlich, who developed Salvarsan (Magic Bullet) to treat syphilis caused by *Treponema pallidum* (Gelpi *et al.*, 2015). Thereafter, the sulphonamide prodrug prontosil was discovered by Gerhard Domagk, which was used to save his daughter's arm from amputation (Otten, 1986). Following this number of sulphonamide group of drugs were developed, although these were largely replaced by the discovery of Penicillins, whose antimicrobial effect was

observed on a contaminated Petri plate by Alexander Fleming in the year 1928 (Fleming, 1929). The discovery of Penicillins led Selman Waksman to study soil-dwelling filamentous “actinomycetes” and this was a major breakthrough in discovering neomycin and streptomycin, the first agents used against tuberculosis. Waksman’s work started the golden age of antibiotic discovery during the era of 1940-1960. Thereafter, a number of classes of antibiotics have been discovered. However, very few antibiotics have been discovered since 1970 and the rate of antimicrobial resistance has been increasing in the modern era. The present article has been proposed to understand the role of compounds or materials which can be used as an alternative to antibiotics, a novel approach to non-antibiotic therapy.

Need for the development of antimicrobial agents as an alternative to antibiotics

1. Antimicrobial resistance
2. Lack of development of new anti-microbial drugs
3. Side effects of antibiotics
4. Indiscriminate use of antibiotics
5. Pharmaceutical research and development is highly expensive

Increasing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) caused the emergence of new resistant phenotypes. Indiscriminate use of antibiotics in medical & veterinary practices and the growing presence of antibiotics in water, soil and food have contributed to the problem of antibiotic resistance. A number of classes of antibiotics were approved by FDA from 1935 to 1970 as shown in table 1. Antimicrobial resistance has developed against different classes of antibiotics. Some of the different pathways through which antimicrobial resistance develops are shown in figure 1.

Fig 1. Mechanism of development of antimicrobial resistance [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

But the production and approval of newer classes of antibiotics decreased from the year 2000. Only three new types of antibiotics have been made available for human use since 2000, and one of those can only be used topically (Spellberg *et al.*, 2008). Hence there is a need to develop an alternative approach to treating infections.

Alternative to antibiotics

To overcome the decreased rate of discovery of new classes of antibiotics and increasing antimicrobial resistance, different compounds having antibacterial effect either bacteriostatic or bactericidal can be synthesized or the compounds which are available can be modified into drugs having an antibacterial effect.

Table 1: Classes of antibiotics were approved by FDA from 1935 to 1970

Antibiotic class	Approval by FDA
Sulfonamides	1935
Penicillin	1941
Aminoglycosides	1944
Cephalosporins	1945
Chloramphenicol	1949
Tetracyclines	1950
Macrolides lincosamides	1952
Glycopeptides	1956
Rifamycins	1957
Nitroimidazoles	1959
Quinolones	1962
Trimethoprim	1968

The present article covers some of the alternatives such as Plants and plant extracts, Nano-Antimicrobial Materials, Phage therapy, antimicrobial peptides, CRISPR-Cas, Immunity modulating agents, and Inhibitors targeting pathogenicity.

Plants and plant extracts

Medicinal plants are defined as a group of plants that possess some special properties that qualify them as articles of drugs and therapeutic agents. Plant extracts, also known as phytobiotics, are used in animal nutrition for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidative, and anti-parasitic activities.

Types of phytochemicals: -

Alkaloids, Glycosides, Flavonoids, Phenolic, Tannins, Terpene, Essential Oils, Phyto-estrogens and Sterols.

Secondary metabolites of plants such as terpenoids (mono- and sesquiterpenes, steroids), tannins,

glycosides, and alkaloids (present as alcohols, aldehydes, ketones, esters, ethers, lactones) are biologically active, which possess antimicrobial activity (Huyghebaert *et al.*, 2011).

Fig 2. Mechanism of antibacterial effect of phytochemicals [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

In the period 1981-2006, 109 new antibacterial agents were approved, out of which, 69% were of natural origin and in the case of antifungal agents 21% were derivatives of natural compounds (Newman, 2008). It has been established that the plant extracts in *in vitro* tests showing minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of around 100-1000 µg/ml possess antibacterial activity (Simoes *et al.*, 2009). Different secondary metabolites of plants have varying mechanisms as shown in figure 2, such as tannins acting on bacterial proteins and enzymes and also causing iron deprivation (Scalbert, 1991). Cryptolepine, an indolequinone alkaloid intercalates bacterial DNA and inhibits topoisomerase (Karou *et al.*, 2005). Saponins interact with bacterial cell membrane and cause damage resulting in cellular destruction (Morrissey and Osbourn, 1999).

Nano-Antimicrobial Materials

Nanomaterials can be used to deliver antimicrobial substances or can either itself act as antimicrobial agent. Metal and metal oxide nanoparticles have shown promising antimicrobial potential due to its less toxicity and enhanced antimicrobial activity (Fernandez-Moure *et al.*, 2017). Nanoparticles

(NPs) have an increased surface to volume ratio, hence they are appropriate drug carriers and also have increased solubility (Wang *et al.*, 2017). Nanoparticles have shown abilities such as disrupting bacterial wall, inhibiting biofilm formation, and generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), thereby damaging the bacterial DNA and proteins (Baptista *et al.*, 2018). For example, Bismuth nanoparticles were synthesized which slowed the spread of the multidrug-resistant *Candida auris* strains in healthcare. The antibacterial activity of different nanoparticles is presented in table 2 and figure 3. One study reported the synthesis of anionic solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) formulations containing *Eugenia caryophyllata* essential oil, having antibacterial and antifungal agent. It was observed that adding the essential oil to SLNs effectively reduced the concentration needed to stop microbial development and kill it (Fazly Bazzaz *et al.*, 2018).

Fig 3. Mechanism of antibacterial effect of different nanoparticles [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

Phage therapy

Bacteriophages are viruses that are parasitic to bacteria and propagate at the expense of bacteria. Phages were used for a long time before conventional antibiotics, discovered by Frederick Twort in UK in 1915 and Félix d'Herell in France in 1917.

The first clinical use was published in Belgium in 1921, in which *Staphylococcus*-specific phage was injected into the boils to treat cutaneous furuncle and carbuncles.

Table 2: Antimicrobial mechanism of different nanoparticles

Nanomaterial	Antimicrobial mechanism
Silver NPs	Disrupts cell membrane and damage DNA
Zinc oxide NPs	Produces H ₂ O ₂ and disrupts the cell membrane
Titanium dioxide NPs	ROS production
Gold NPs	Electrostatic interaction with cell membrane
Chitosan NPs	Increased membrane permeability and rupture
Fullerenes	Enhance the activity of neutrophils and decrease membrane integrity
Carbon nanotubes	ROS production and oxidation of cell membrane and lipids
Nitric oxide releasing NPs	Release NO; Nitrosative stress
Nanoemulsion	Disruption of spore coat

Reports suggest that phages have preventive effects on pathogens such as *E. coli* O157:H7, Salmonella and Campylobacter (Huff *et al.*, 2005; Johnson *et al.*, 2008). In 2006, US FDA approved a phage cocktail containing 6 types of pure bacteriophages which was named as LMP-102TM to prevent contamination of meat by listeria.

The mechanism of antimicrobial activity involves the attachment of phage to the bacterial cell surface followed by the injection of genetic material into bacterial cytoplasm, which results in the synthesis of phage components by hijacking host cell machinery (Figure 4). New phage components are produced which results in bacterial cell lysis releasing phage progenies. This mechanism can be exploited to treat various infections caused by bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, Shigella, and Salmonella.

Fig 4. Interaction of bacteriophage with bacteria and bacterial cell lysis [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

Antimicrobial peptides

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) also known as host defense peptides are synthesized by multicellular organisms against invading pathogens (Hancock and Sahl, 2006). AMPs are generally amphiphilic in nature in which its cationic domain interacts with the positively charged cell surface of bacteria while the hydrophobic domain interacts with the lipid moieties of the bacterial cell, thereby causing the destruction of bacterial cells (Figure 5) (Mahlpuu *et al.*, 2016). The AMPs are non-toxic to mammalian cells as they are zwitterionic in nature, hence they do not interact with the positively charged components. FDA approved a biomimetic peptide called enfuvirtide (Fuzeon) for combination therapy against HIV (Fung and Guo, 2004). Different types of AMPs and their characteristics are shown in table 3.

Antimicrobial peptides are generally of two types: non-ribosomal AMPs and ribosomal AMPs. The AMPs are mainly produced by bacteria and examples of non-ribosomal peptides include bacitracin, polymyxin, and gramicidin. On the other hand, ribosomal AMPs can be from mammalian, plants, insects, viruses, or bacterial source.

Fig 5. Antimicrobial action of peptides [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

Biotechnology-based alternative therapeutics: -

CRISPR-Cas

Clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)-Cas is a feature adopted by bacteria and archaea as a protective measure against bacteriophages (Barrangou *et al.*, 2007). In this, spacers which are short sequences obtained from bacteriophages or plasmids are inserted into the bacterial genome as CRISPR array, thereafter the Cas protein machinery will utilize the guide RNAs from the spacers for the specific targeting of the invading nucleic acid having the same sequence (Pursey *et al.*, 2018).

CRISPR-Cas systems are classified into two classes: class I comprises types I, III, and IV, while class II consists of types II, V, and VI (Pursey *et al.*, 2018). CRISPR-Cas has been shown to selectively target the AMR genes of bacteria and initiate its removal from the bacterial population (Figure 6) (Bikard *et al.*, 2014).

This leads to the sensitization of bacteria to antibiotics to which it has earlier developed resistance. Additionally, CRISPR-Cas9 phagemids have shown *in vivo* effect by killing specific bacteria (Bikard *et al.*, 2014).

Table 3: Different types of peptides and their characteristic

Type	Characteristic	AMPs
Anionic peptides	Contains glutamic and aspartic acid	Dermcidin from humans
Linear cationic alpha-helical peptides	Lacks cysteine	Melittin from insects; LL37 from humans
Cationic peptide enriched for specific amino acid	Contains glycine, proline, arginine, tryptophan, phenylalanine	Prophenin from pigs; Indolicidin from cattle
Anionic and cationic peptides that contain cysteine and form disulfide bonds	Have 1-3 disulfide bonds	1 bond- Brevinins 2 bonds- Protegrin from pigs 3 bonds- Defensins from humans

Nano sized CRISPR (polymer-derivatized Cas9 complexed with single guide RNA) has been developed. It targets the mec-A gene involved in methicillin resistance (Kang *et al.*, 2017).

Immunity modulating agents

Immunity modulating agents also called ‘immunomodulators’ are used for immunotherapy, which is defined as the treatment of disease by inducing, enhancing, or suppressing an immune response. Among the immunity modulating agents, the vaccine is one of the most important while other pharmaceutical agents could also be used as immunomodulators.

Traditional vaccines are generally classified into live-attenuated and inactivated/killed vaccines. However, the major drawbacks of the live strains are that they persist in the animal body for a longer time (Tan *et al.*, 1997) and have a high risk of reverting to full virulence (Barrow, 2007). Killed vaccines also have disadvantages such as the lack of relevant protective antigens due to *in vitro* growth conditions (Gast, 2007).

Sub-unit vaccine is introduced as an alternative to live and killed vaccine, which is composed of either a single antigen or multiple defined antigens. Meanwhile, subunit vaccines require formulation with an appropriate adjuvant as they are poorly immunogenic, (Mutwiri *et al.*, 2011).

Fig 6. CRISPR Cas9 mediated deletion of antimicrobial resistance gene (AMR) [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

DNA vaccines offer another promising improvement to conventional vaccines. When the DNA vaccine is injected into the cells of body, the host cells “read” the DNA and convert it into pathogenic proteins which would trigger a range of immune responses.

Other immunomodulators such as “immunostimulants” are able to nonspecifically enhance the innate immune function and improve the host’s resistance to diseases. Since the 1990s, nucleotides, thymosin, and oregano oil have mainly been used as immunostimulants. Probiotics, herbs, and their extracts later became the focus of experiments as immunostimulants (Thacker, 2010). It has been proposed that adding immunostimulants to animal diet can enhance their natural defences, giving them tolerance to diseases under stressful situations like grading, reproduction, transfer, and immunization (Bricknell and Dalmo, 2005). Overall, immunotherapy can be used in conjunction with antibiotic therapy to modify the immune response (Kak *et al.*, 2012).

Inhibitors targeting pathogenicity

Quorum sensing inhibitors

Bacterial colony has a quorum sensing (QS) system which regulates and controls their pathogenicity (Swift *et al.*, 2001) and has self-induced signaling molecules (auto-inducers, AIs), receptors, and downstream regulatory proteins. The function of the QS system can be blocked by some inhibitors which specifically target the QS, thus preventing bacterial virulence regulated by QS system

(Figure 7). QS inhibitors (QSIs) are classified into three groups: non-peptide small molecule, peptide, and protein QSIs. Non peptide QSIs are N-acyl homoserine lactones (AHLs) analogs which inhibit the synthesis of the QS signalling molecules.

Biofilm-inhibitors

Bacteria forming biofilms have been shown to cause chronic infections as they become tolerant to antibiotics and disinfectant chemicals. Additionally, biofilm resists phagocytosis and other components of the immune system (Hoiby *et al.*, 2010). Enzymes such as polysaccharide hydrolases (Kaplan *et al.*, 2004), DNases (Izano *et al.*, 2008), proteases (Marti *et al.*, 2010), and alginate lyases have shown promising results in dissolving biofilm matrix.

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Fig 7. Quorum sensing inhibitors and biofilm inhibitors mediated inhibition of antimicrobial resistance [Pictorial representation is designed manually by using an online tool (Biorender)]

Reports have suggested that DNases and alginate lyase degrade the biofilm matrix of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and thus enhance the activity of tobramycin against biofilm (Alipour *et al.*, 2009). Another study has shown the combined effect of Urokinase or lumbrokinase with fleroxacin which significantly inhibited the *P. aeruginosa* biofilms (Selan *et al.*, 1993).

Conclusion

With the increasing demand, consumption and decreased rate of production of newer classes of antibiotics, there is a need to conduct some different strategies to combat diseases by adopting a non-antibiotic approach which involves the use of plants, phage therapy, antimicrobial peptides, nanomaterials, and many more, in order to produce novel compounds which not only have antimicrobial properties but also inhibit the developing antimicrobial resistance in order to improve the health and welfare of the humans and livestock.

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